

SPARSE PROJECTIONS AND MOTION ESTIMATION IN COLOUR FILTER ARRAYS

Alexander Sibiryakov

Visual Information Laboratory, Mutsubishi Electric ITE-BV,
 20, Frederick Sanger Road, Guildford, GU2 7YD, United Kingdom
 Phone: + 44 1483 885828, fax: +44 1483 579107, email: Alexander.Sibiryakov@vil.ite.mee.com
 Web: http://www.vil.ite.mee.com/

ABSTRACT

Integral image projection, computed by summing pixel rows or columns, is one of the standard tools used in computer vision algorithms for image analysis. We propose methods of reducing the complexity of image projection computation. The algorithm skips some pixels during pixel-by-pixel scanning, while preserving the resolution of original image projections. The approximated or "sparse" projections can replace the standard projections in any image processing algorithm, enabling low-cost solutions. Particularly, we consider projection-based dominant motion estimation in video and confirm the method's effectiveness by experimental results. Some variants of sparse projections can be applied directly to Colour Filter Array (CFA) images, thus allowing the algorithm to obtain high-level information on camera motion at the lowest level stage in the image processing pipeline.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many image processing algorithms use image projections (Fig. 1a) to reduce a two-dimensional problem to a set of one-dimensional problems [1,2]. The main reasons for such reduction are: 1) in some cases it is easier to detect objects or image features in 1D projection functions than in 2D image functions; 2) 1D problems are much less computationally complex than 2D problems. For a $W \times H$ pixel image, even a simple pixel-by-pixel scan is of $O(WH)$ complexity, and the algorithms usually consist of multiple scans. By image scan we mean here a general image processing algorithm that visits each pixel using nested column-by-column and row-by-row loops. The projection-based algorithm, e.g., motion estimation described below, requires one image scan to compute image projections and a few projection scans with $O(W+H)$ complexity. Each value of the horizontal/vertical projection is obtained by summing all pixels in the corresponding column/ row, shown schematically in Fig.1b. Thus, the number of additions, N_p , for computing both projections, is $2WH$.

In a real-time system, especially in those implemented in low-cost DSP boards, even $O(WH)$ projection computation complexity of may be insufficient for real-time performance. Downsampling the image by a factor of m reduces the number of additions to WH/m^2 , but proportionally reduces the projections' resolution and the accuracy of the results obtained by processing such projections. Also, the downsampling process itself may require an additional number of operations proportional to WH .

In this work we propose methods of further reducing this complexity by factors of 2, 3, 4... In Section 2 we show how to compute approximated image projections and show that such approximations can be used in image processing algorithms in the same way as standard projections.

The low-cost algorithm for dominant motion estimation in video, presented in [2], is based on the fact that the dominant

image translation translates of image projections. One of the earliest works on this topic was reported in [1], which uses image projections in the general problem of image registration. Method [2] uses horizontal and vertical image projections, computed from successive video frames, to estimate components of the dominant motion (Fig.2). In Section 3 we apply this method using approximated image projections.

Another aspect of the presented work is the application of the motion estimation method to colour filter arrays (CFAs), used in the majority of digital video cameras. CFA is a monochromatic light sensor producing a mosaic image, in which each pixel's location contains either a red, green or blue sample. The commonly-used Bayer pattern CFA [3] captures pixels by groups of four: two green, one red and one blue sample. To extract an RGB-image from the Bayer pattern, many demosaicing methods have been developed. A good survey can be found in [4]. To interpolate colour values at each pixel, Bayer proposed simple bilinear interpolation [3]. Advanced methods use edge detection [5] and spectral models [6] to reduce artefacts in demosaiced CFA

Figure 1 - Standard projection computation. (a) Projections of three colour channels of a real image; (b) Schematic representation of projection computation, where sum of pixels in each row (or column) determines the corresponding value (shown by an arrow) of the projection function. The scanned pixels are marked by dots.

Figure 2 - Horizontal camera-motion estimation between three successive video frames by estimating 1D-shifts between horizontal projections. The vertical motion is estimated similarly.

Most of the image processing methods, including motion estimation algorithms, require the final colour image, obtained by demosaicing the CFA. The design of methods directly applicable to CFA images opens the possibility of getting high-level information at the lowest level stage of image processing. In Section 4 we discuss such an application of the projection-based motion estimation method to the CFA images. The experimental results are presented in Section 5.

2. SPARSE PROJECTIONS

In this section we introduce *sparse projections* or, simply, S_n -*projections* where n is an elementary block size. The non-overlapping blocks of $n \times n$ pixels cover the entire image and each block is used to update exactly n values of the horizontal S_n -projection and exactly n values of the vertical S_n -projection. According to the definition, the standard projections (Fig.1) can also be called S_1 -*projections*, indicating that the elementary blocks consist of one pixel. The S_n -projection has the same length as the standard projection; therefore the image resolution is preserved. The algorithm of S_n -projection computation scans an image while avoiding some pixels by: 1) row/column skipping, 2) diagonal skipping; 3) block permutation. Fig.3 schematically illustrates these methods.

The row/column skipping method uses two image scans; each computes the corresponding projection. Each n th row is used to compute the horizontal projection. Similarly, each n th column is used to compute the vertical projection. This method can also be illustrated by a block-based representation. Fig.3a shows examples with 2×2 and 3×3 blocks. The 2×2 -example shows that algorithm's computational complexity is proportional to $3WH/4$, as only three pixels are used in each block. For the general case of an $n \times n$ block the computational complexity is $C_{row/col}(n) = k_1(2n-1)WH/n^2$, where the constant k_1 accounts for additional overhead due to image scanning. The number of additions $N_{row/col}$ this method requires is obtained from the facts that $2(n-1)$ pixels from a block are added to projections once, and that only one pixel from the block is used twice: $N_{row/col}(n) = 2WH/n \leq N_0$.

The diagonal skipping method (Fig.3b) skips some image diagonals to compute S_n -projections. It uses only pixels (u,v) that satisfy $(u+v) \bmod n = 0$. This means that in each elementary block, only the pixels from the main diagonal are used; therefore this method's complexity C_{diag} is proportional to n (the number of pixels in the main diagonal of each block) multiplied by the number of blocks WH/n^2 : $C_{diag} = k_2WH/n$, where the constant k_2 takes into account the computation of positions of diagonal pixels and other overhead. From experimental testing we found that $C_{diag} < C_{row/col}$. Each pixel belonging to the block's diagonal is used twice, therefore the number of additions is: $N_{diag}(n) = 2WH/n$.

We modify the diagonal skipping method to introduce the third method of S_n -projection computation (Fig.3c). This method preliminarily transforms each elementary block by row (or, equivalently, column) permutation (Fig.4). A random or a regular set of permutations can be used. The computational complexity C_{perm} is similar to the diagonal skipping method's: $C_{perm} = k_3WH/n$, but a more complex algorithm scans the image. In the efficient implementation of the scanning algorithm the pixel positions (Fig.4) should be pre-computed. The constant k_3 takes into account the scanning algorithm's complexity, and generally $C_{diag} < C_{perm}$. This method uses n pixels from each block twice to contribute to both horizontal and vertical projections, therefore the number of additions is: $N_{perm}(n) = 2WH/n$.

All three methods described above require an equal number of elementary operations (additions) to compute the projections: $N_{row/col}(n) = N_{diag}(n) = N_{perm}(n)$, while the total time required by the

diagonal skipping method is generally less than the time required by the other two methods.

Fig.5 shows an example of projection computation by the proposed methods. Qualitative and numerical comparisons of sparse projections computed by the proposed methods lead to the following conclusions. All three methods give similar results for $n=2,3$ and 4. S_n -projections obtained using such block sizes do not deviate significantly from the standard S_1 -projection. Fig.5 shows that S_2 - and S_4 -projections practically coincide with the black curve corresponding to S_1 . Starting from $n > 4$ the projections become

Figure 3 – Sparse projection computation by different methods. 1st and 2nd columns are schematic representations of the method for block sizes $n=2,3$. Only the marked pixels are used to compute the projections. Black pixels are used to compute both projections. The third column shows a fragment of the real image from Fig.1a, where the skipped pixels in blocks of size $n=2$ are shown in white.

Figure 4 - Elementary 3×3 blocks, generated by row (or, equivalently, column) permutations

Figure 5 - S_n -projection computation using three methods: top – row/column skipping; middle – diagonal skipping; bottom – block permutation. The horizontal projection of the green channel of the image in Fig.1 is shown. Block sizes $n=1,2,4,8$ and 16 were used in each method. For demonstration purposes the intensity of each curve is proportional to n : the black curve is the S_1 -projection; and the lightest curve is the S_{16} -projection. The right column shows zoomed fragments of the curves. Note that S_2 and S_4 are very close to S_1 .

noisy and some artefacts appear. In Fig.5 the S_8 -projection (light curve) and S_{16} -projection (the lightest curve) differ from the other curves in detail, but the general appearance of the S_7 -projection is preserved. S_n -projections obtained by row/column skipping can significantly deviate from standard S_7 -projections. Systematic shifts in value, but not in position, appear due to image regions with colour gradients. Also, the curves obtained by this method are less noisy than the curves obtained by other methods. Projections obtained by the diagonal skipping method oscillate around standard projections. One reason for this behaviour is the colour gradient presented in the image. Some random large differences can also be observed. Projections obtained by block permutation are similar to the standard projection with random noise added. These projections have fewer artefacts than the projections obtained by other methods, but much more noise.

Therefore, S_n -projections can be used instead of standard projections in signal analysis algorithms, taking image projections as input, if such algorithms are robust to noise and small artefacts.

3. FAST DOMINANT MOTION ESTIMATION

The main idea of the fast motion estimation method [2] is to convert 2D image information to 1D signals (projections) at an early stage of processing. The dominant translation between video frames is obtained by estimating each translation component independently as a shift between corresponding projections (Fig.2). Any state-of-the-art signal shift estimation method can be used, e.g., normalized cross-correlation, sum of absolute (or squared) differences or phase correlation.

We adapted this method to use sparse S_n -projections instead of standard projections. Taking into account the analysis from the previous section, we recommend using S_n -projections with block sizes of $n < 5$, as estimated motion values can be affected by noise in S_n -projections.

The block-scheme of our implementation is shown in Fig.6. The dominant motion estimation method consists of two main blocks: image descriptor extraction and descriptor matching. The descriptor consists of two independent parts: a horizontal H-descriptor and a vertical V-descriptor. Depending on the shift estimation method, the descriptor can be the S_n -projection itself (for the estimation in signal domain) or the Fourier transform of S_n -projection (for estimation in frequency domain). The descriptor matching block estimates the shift using descriptors from the current and previous frames.

Experimentally we found that the phase correlation is more robust to noise and small artefacts in S_n -projections than estimation in signal domain. The method is based on the Shift Theorem for the Fourier Transform, from which it follows that if two signals (S_n -projections), say $s_1(x)$ and $s_2(x)$, differ only by translation a : $s_2(x) = s_1(x+a)$, then applying the phase correlation method yields

$$C = F^{-1} \left\{ \frac{F(s_1)F^*(s_2)}{|F(s_1)F^*(s_2)|} \right\} = F^{-1} \left\{ \frac{F(s_1)}{|F(s_1)|} \left(\frac{F(s_2)}{|F(s_2)|} \right)^* \right\},$$

where $F(s)/|F(s)|$ is the normalized Fourier transform of signal s , and $F^*(s)$ is the complex conjugation of $F(s)$, we obtain a pulse at the translation value: $C(x) = \delta(x-a)$. This translation is determined by finding the highest peak in the resulting signal $C(x)$. Fitting a polynomial in the peak's neighbourhood helps to estimate a subpixel amendment to the translation value.

4. DOMINANT MOTION ESTIMATION IN CFA

The Bayer pattern approach [3] uses a special pattern (Fig.7a) as one of the many possible implementations of CFA. Most other

implementations use the principle that the luminance channel (green) is sampled at a higher rate than the chromatic channels (red and blue). The choice of green as representative of the luminance is explained by the fact that the human eye's luminance response curve is close to the frequency of green light [4].

The projections used in the motion estimation method from Section 3 can be computed from: 1) any RGB-image channel (preferably green, usually having the largest dynamic range); 2)

Figure 6 - Block-scheme of the dominant motion estimation method

Figure 7 – (a) Example of Bayer pattern; (b) Proposed method of projection computation using green channel of Bayer pattern

Figure 8 - Image processing pipeline in the conventional and proposed approaches to motion estimation. The "motion estimation" block in both block-schemes corresponds to Fig.6

Figure 9 - Image motion estimation in Bayer pattern CFA.

image intensity, derived from all colour channels; 3) Y-channel of the $Y_C C_b C_r$ colour space, usually available in the camera buffer via camera API; or 4) any other combination of original or processed colour channels. Therefore, the projection-based method requires processing the CFA-image and converting it to a standard colour image. A general image processing pipeline in a digital camera consists of spatial demosaicing followed by colour and gamma correction (Fig.8, upper block scheme).

We propose the design of a fast motion estimation algorithm working directly with CFA images as shown in Figs.7, 8 and 9. This is accomplished by using S_n -projections computed by diagonal skipping or block permutation methods. If we consider $n=2$ (Fig.3a, left column), this pattern exactly corresponds to the Bayer pattern's green channel (Fig.7) or the CMY-Bayer pattern's yellow channel. By adjusting the permutation set in the block permutation method, different CFAs can be modelled, although partial colour interpolation still may be required for complex CFAs. The proposed approach can use the result of motion estimation, as shown by the dashed arrow in Fig.8, for advanced in-camera processing (noise and motion blur reduction, multi-frame-based demosaicing).

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As our other work [2] has already demonstrated the applicability of projection-based motion estimation in video, we mainly focused on the extension of the method using sparse projections and its application to CFA video frames (Section 4). The method has been tested using many standard and our own video sequences. The Bayer CFA video frames were modelled from original RGB frames by channel sampling. In this section we show the results obtained in two sequences: "Stefan" (CIF, 352×288 pix.), which is one of the standard sequences in the video coding area, and "Playground" (QVGA, 320×240) captured by an intensively shaking a hand-held camera.

In each frame of the test sequence the motion vector has been estimated using projections of CFA's green channel (method S_2 -CFA) and compared to motion vectors estimated by other projection-based methods described in this paper: 1) standard projections (method S_1) as in [2]; 2) projections obtained by row/column skipping with block size $n=3$ (method S_3 -row/col) and 3) projections obtained by block permutation with block size $n=4$ (method S_4 -perm.). Also, we implemented a feature-based motion estimator, in which feature locations are determined as local maxima of the Harris corner detector. For each feature a local neighbourhood of $[-d,d] \times [-d,d]$ pixels is considered in the previous frame and the feature with the largest correlation coefficient is selected. $d=30$ pixels was used in the "Stefan" sequence; $d=40$ pixels was used in the "Playground" sequence. The set of feature correspondences is further processed with the RANSAC estimator to find the motion vector.

To show frame alignment quality, we use a space-time representation of aligned projections (see Fig.10 for "Stefan" and Fig.13 for "Playground"). Similar representation has been used also in [7] for video warping. We use mappings $(u,v,N) \rightarrow (X,N)$ and $(u,v,N) \rightarrow (Y,N)$, where (u,v) is a location in the original N th video frame and (X,Y) are global positions of the video frames obtained by accumulating estimated motion vectors (x,y) . Each frame N is represented by its horizontal and vertical RGB projections positioned in the global coordinate system (X,Y) . RGB projection functions are represented by 1D RGB-images. Note that RGB projection are used for demonstration only; the motion vectors are estimated by S_2 -CFA (using projections of CFA green channel).

Experimental results for the "Stefan" sequence are shown in Figs.10-12. This sequence contains rapid camera motions and

multiple zoom-ins and zoom-outs, visible in Fig.10(b,c) as an expanding/collapsing optical flow. Motion vector values (x,y) measured in pixels are shown in Fig.11a depending on frame number. These motion vectors are used to accumulate absolute positions of the frames, shown in Fig.10(b,c). Figure 11(b-e) shows differences between the motion graph in Fig.11a and motion graphs obtained by the methods S_1 , S_3 -row/col, S_4 -perm and feature-based. These graphs show that the translation values estimated by different methods are close to each other and that the error is usually less than 1-2 pixels. The largest differences in values can be observed in the frames corresponding to rapid camera motion and camera zoom. Figure 12 shows two examples of high-level results derived from low-level motion analysis in CFA: a background mosaic, obtained by shifting each RGB-frame by its accumulated motion vector (X,Y) ; and a foreground mask of the tennis player, obtained by shifting each frame, subtracting two aligned successive frames and thresholding the absolute difference.

Experimental results for the "Playground" sequence are shown in Figs.13-14. The motion from Fig.13(b,c) was estimated using S_2 -CFA method. The motion in Fig.13(d,e) was estimated by the feature-based algorithm, not related to image projections. We provide projection-based representation only for visual comparison with Fig.13(b,c). A graph of the motion vector depending on number of the frame, is shown in Fig.14a. Only the x-component of the motion vector is shown; the y-component's behaviour is similar, which is visible from the accumulated motion in Fig.13(b,c). Similarly to Fig.11, the motion vectors have been compared to the results obtained by S_1 , S_3 -row/col, S_4 -perm and feature-based methods. The comparison graphs show that the translation values estimated by different projection-based methods are close to each other, and that the error is usually less than two pixels, but a few gross errors up to five pixels are presented. In this sequence with intense camera shaking and significant motion blur, the lowest-level CFA-based algorithm performs better than the high-level feature-based motion estimator. This is visible from comparison of the aligned projections in Fig.13. In the motion graph difference (Fig.14e), a few gross errors in motion, up to 35 pixels, can be observed. While projections are integral features of the entire image, interest points are obtained from a local detector. Due to motion blur, the locations of interest points are less reliable than in a blur-free case. This results in low correlation values and erroneous translation, estimated by RANSAC.

Table 1 demonstrates superior performance of sparse projections in terms of average CPU time required by both descriptor extraction and matching modules. S_2 -CFA method can work alone at 1000ms/0.41ms $\approx$ 2440 CIF frames-per-second rate, or leave more than 32ms (assuming 30fps real-time requirements) for other image processing tasks, such as CFA demosaicing. For comparison, our implementation of feature-based motion estimation method requires about 100ms per CIF-frame (10fps).

S_1	S_2 -CFA	S_3 -row/col	S_4 -perm
0.80ms	0.41 ms	0.38 ms	0.35 ms

Table 1 – CPU load per video frame for different projection-based motion estimation algorithms applied in "Stefan" sequence. The test platform is Pentium-M, 1.8 GHz

6. CONCLUSIONS

Sparse projections computed by the presented methods can replace the standard projections in image processing algorithms without affecting the accuracy of the results and enabling high performance. We have shown that sparse projections can be effectively employed for dominant motion estimation, which is an essential part of such applications as video stabilization, object

detection from a free-moving camera and video coding. Directly using CFA images allows motion estimation at the earliest stage of the in-camera image-processing pipeline, avoiding expensive colour interpolation and correction algorithms. The motion information can be used in the following stages of camera-image processing; for example, for advanced colour interpolation, to reduce the motion blur or for denoising the CFA image before its demosaicing, using a stack of previous CFA frames.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank Dr. Miroslaw Bober and Dr. Paul Ratliff from Visual Information Laboratory, Mutsubishi Electric ITE-B.V. for helpful discussions and contribution to this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.Alliney, C.Morandi, "Digital image registration using projections," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence-8, No.2, pp.222-223, March 1986
- [2] A.Sibiryakov, M.Bober, "Real-Time Multi-Frame Analysis of Dominant Translation," In Proc. of the 18th International Conference on Pattern Recognition, Vol.1, pp 55- 58, 2006
- [3] B.Bayer."Color imaging array," U.S.Patent 3,971,065, 1976.
- [4] R.Ramanath, W. Snyder, G. Bilbro, W. Sander. "Demosaicking methods for Bayer colour arrays," Journal of Electronic Imaging, 11(3), July 2002.
- [5] R.Hibbard. "Apparatus and method for adaptively interpolating a full color image utilizing luminance gradients," U.S.Patent 5,382,976, 1995.
- [6] N.Lian, L.Chang, Y.Tan, "Improved colour filter array demosaicking by accurate luminance estimation," IEEE Int. Conf. on Image Processing, Vol.1, pp.41-44, Sept.2005
- [7] A.Rav-Acha, Y.Pritch, D.Lischinski, S.Peleg, "Evolving Time Fronts: Spatio-Temporal Video Warping," Hebrew University Technical Report HUJI-CSE-LTR-2005-10, April 2005.

Figure 10 – Dominant motion in the “Stefan” sequence obtained by S_2 -CFA method. (a) 1st frame of the original sequence; spatio-temporal alignments of horizontal and vertical RGB-projections are shown in figures (b) and (c) respectively.

Figure 11 – Experimental results for the “Stefan” sequence. (a) Graph of the motion vector values (x,y) measured in pixels, depending on number of the frame. Horizontal between-frame shifts achieve 25pixels, while in the vertical direction the camera is almost steady. (b)-(e) Differences between the motion graph (a) and motion graphs obtained by other methods. In all cases the error is less than two pixels.

Figure 12 – High-level results derived from low-level motion analysis in CFA. (a) Background mosaic; (b) Foreground mask of the tennis player.

Figure 13 - Dominant motion in the “Playground” sequence obtained by two methods: S_2 -CFA and feature-based. (a) 1st frame of the original sequence; (b),(c) spatio-temporal alignment of horizontal and vertical RGB projections using S_2 -CFA method; (d),(e) spatio-temporal alignment of horizontal and vertical projections using feature-based method (note the feature-based method’s poor performance).

Figure 14 - Experimental results for the “Playground” sequence. (a) Graph of the motion x-component measured in pixels, depending on number of the frame. (b)-(e) differences between the motion graph (a) and motion graphs obtained by other methods.